

TENSION, COMPRESSION, AND BEND PROPERTIES
FOR SiC/RBSN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The room-temperature tension, compression, and bend properties of unidirectional SiC fiber-reinforced reaction-bonded silicon nitride composites (SiC/RBSN) have been investigated. The effects of fiber content on the modulus, first matrix cracking strength, and ultimate strength properties were determined. In tension, composites with greater than 8% fiber content showed strain capability beyond matrix fracture and fiber dominated ultimate strength. In compression, the composites displayed essentially elastic behavior, and matrix-dominated ultimate strength. For both deformation modes, most mechanical properties increased with fiber content. In bend, the modulus, strength properties, and failure modes of the composites were influenced by span to thickness ratio. To avoid shear delamination, a span to thickness ratio of 20 or greater was required.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Ceramics; SiC Fiber-Reinforced Silicon Nitride; Testing/Evaluation/Characterization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Considerable interest has been shown by researchers in recent years for the development of fiber-reinforced ceramic matrix composites (FRCMC) for advanced heat engine applications. This interest stems from the fact that FRCMC can provide microstructural mechanisms for improved toughness while maintaining the advantages of monolithic ceramics, namely, high temperature strength, low density, and oxidation resistance. In addition the properties of the FRCMC can be tailored for specific applications. By choosing high strength, high modulus fibers that are compatible with the matrix and by controlling the fiber/matrix interface properties, researchers have been able to fabricate a variety of strong, tough FRCMC such as, silicon carbide fiber-reinforced reaction-bonded silicon nitride (SiC/RBSN) [1-5]. To determine the full potential of these materials for engine applications studies are needed to evaluate their deformation behavior and failure mechanisms under various stress states. Thus, the objective of